

European Digital Media Observatory

EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives

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EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives

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Introduction

This set of principles and guidelines for effective media literacy initiatives has been developed by EDMO's [Working Group on Media Literacy Standards and Best Practices](#) with input from the EDMO Hubs and other practitioners and experts during a consultation process. Its goal is to increase the effectiveness of media literacy initiatives across Europe by developing guidelines that new and existing practitioners can consult. This is crucial to EDMO's wider mission, since better media literacy is likely to increase the public's resilience to online mis- and disinformation.

For the purposes of this work, we based our definition of media literacy on that of the European Commission's [Media Literacy Expert Group](#): *media literacy is an umbrella expression that includes all the technical, cognitive, social, civic and creative capacities that allow a person to access, have a critical understanding of the media and interact and engage with it.*

This document has been designed for use by anyone involved in the development of media literacy initiatives – civil society, educators, policy makers, those in the media or tech industries. In an area as complex and diverse as media literacy, there can be no one-size-fits-all approach. Media literacy initiatives – such as training courses, published lesson plans or other resources, online games, or campaigns – vary considerably in scope, size, duration and focus. As a result, not all of these guidelines will be relevant to all projects. It is entirely up to the user to select the most appropriate advice for their initiative.

In an area as complex and diverse as media literacy, there can be no one-size-fits-all approach. It is entirely up to the user to select the most appropriate advice for their initiative.

While EDMO's focus is disinformation, the guidelines can be applied widely across diverse media literacy initiatives. For example, these might include news literacy initiatives, which will have a greater focus on the value of independent journalism in the media ecosystem; wider digital literacy initiatives, which will focus on explaining how digital media operate and how to use them; algo-literacy initiatives, which will focus on understanding the role of algorithms in our media consumption, or many more.

The guidelines checklist is intended to be helpful in raising issues for consideration, based on the experiences of prior media literacy initiatives. It should not become a 'tick box' exercise or be used to limit flexibility in developing future initiatives.

About the guidelines

We have grouped the guidelines under 12 principles, and grouped these into three sections: development, delivery and review.

Development

A good media literacy initiative:

- **has clearly defined goals and principles**
- **is empowering**
- **promotes critical understanding of the media ecosystem**
- **consultative and relevant**
- **takes an evidence-based approach**
- **is inclusive**
- **is ethical and accessible**

Delivery

A good media literacy initiative:

- **is transparent**
- **is prepared**
- **is adaptable**

Review

A good media literacy initiative:

- **endures**
- **reflects, shares and evaluates**

We aim to keep the guidelines concise, with links to further explanation and examples when necessary. In the longer term, we intend to make these guidelines available in multiple languages, and to include localised examples and resources for application in national and regional contexts across Europe.

Consultation process

The first draft of the guidelines was developed by the dedicated EDMO Working Group, and was then shared with media literacy experts across the 14 EDMO national and multinational Hubs. In December 2023, we held a consultation event attended by 78 members of the wider media literacy expert community, where the guidelines were presented and discussed in smaller groups. Feedback was collated and discussed, and a draft version of the guidelines was published for wider consultation in March 2024 following a presentation at the Media Literacy Matters conference. The Working Group is very grateful for all the insightful comments received which have been incorporated as far as possible in this version.

Development

Key goals and principles

- ✓ **A good media literacy initiative has clearly defined goals and principles**

Develop clearly defined, achievable, and explicit goals for an initiative

- Define clear goals at the beginning of an initiative to allow for more focused, targeted work and with the potential for more rigorous and effective assessment and evaluation of these goals. A period of knowledge gathering can help to inform such goals. It is important to bear in mind that these goals might evolve during the course of the project and may be updated and redefined.
- Connect with existing recognised frameworks and skills measures, at a national or international level. For example, the [European Digital Competence Framework for all citizens](#) (DigComp) aims to create a common language and understanding of digital competence requirements and development goals among the multiple stakeholders involved in digital skills initiatives.

Establish your key principles

- Identify some key principles to guide your work.
- For example, UNESCO has developed what it calls [five laws of media and information literacy](#), ERGA's Action Group on Media Literacy [has identified](#) a set of six key principles to consider, NAMLE's [resources](#) provide a guide to principles, and Ofcom [proposes principles](#) for media literacy design (targeted at online platforms).

Define your target audience

- Knowing your target audience is essential, and it is important not to forget about minorities within a target group. It is worth noting that even within one demographic, existing skill levels and needs are likely to be varied.
- Therefore, it can be helpful to conduct knowledge gathering activities with the audience such as focus groups, observations or surveys to better understand their habits and needs.

- ✓ **A good media literacy initiative is empowering**

Ensure that the initiative takes an empowering rather than solely protectionist approach

- Media literacy skills are clearly vital for promoting online safety and preventing online harms, and much of the funding in this area is likely to be targeted at prevention of/protection against harm, particularly when it comes to vulnerable audiences. However, as decades of research suggest, it is important to think about how media literacy skills

and knowledge can empower participants to explore and to create media, as well as to protect them from harm.

- Empowering participants can happen in various ways: for example, by recognising and celebrating the existing knowledge and skills of participants, by encouraging peer support, or by ensuring dialogue between those leading the initiative and the participants.

Consider possible negative outcomes, and take steps to reduce any potential harms

- Even with the best of intentions, your project might have unexpected negative outcomes, and it is important to be aware of what these might be. For example, could participants end up becoming distrustful of all information, even that from legitimate sources, as a result of a fear of ‘fake news’? Could an increase in digital skills without an accompanying increase in critical thinking capability result in behaviour that is harmful to others?

A good media literacy initiative promotes critical understanding of the digital media ecosystem

Improve your audience’s critical thinking skills

- Understanding how the media ecosystem works and building related critical thinking skills is crucial for developing resilience to mis- and disinformation, hate speech, bullying, scams and fraud, social media ‘addiction’ as well as other potential online harms. It will also enable people to engage more creatively and constructively with the online world, to value rigorous, independent journalism and to make informed media choices.
- Depending on the focus of the initiative, this could include explaining the role, history and business models of independent journalism (including public service journalism), of technology companies and their products, of influencers and other advertisers, and the role of policy makers and regulators. This could include explaining the flow of data online and who owns it, thinking about the motivations and interests of those who publish information and about bias, or promoting critical understanding of concepts like the ‘attention economy’ and ‘filter bubbles’.

Exploring the wider context

A good media literacy initiative is consultative and relevant

Consult your target audience and when possible involve them in project design

- In conjunction with the needs analysis, it is essential to include the perspectives of your target audience in the planning and design of an initiative. Consultation might have an impact on the language used, on accessibility requirements, and consideration of equality and inclusion, and will increase the likelihood that your project is relevant to your audience and their lives, accessible, and effective in achieving its goals.
- Remember that your audience may have very different media practices and habits to other sectors of the population, and even to others with similar demographic profiles.

Ensure your approach involves as many relevant stakeholders as possible

- When appropriate, partner with expert organisations who already reach these audiences and have a trusted relationship with them: media literacy work often relates to people's deeply held beliefs, values and the individuals of institutions they trust, so having an established relationship with audiences is particularly important.

A good media literacy initiative takes an evidence-based approach

Use an established pedagogical framework with sound learning objectives

- This is essential for any initiatives that involve education or training, whether for children or adults. This should demonstrate awareness of and alignment with educational curricula in the countries involved, as well as established pedagogical practices applied in informal learning settings and adult learning. These [Guidelines for teachers and educators on tackling disinformation and promoting digital literacy through education and training](#) produced by the EC provide a comprehensive description of different teaching and learning approaches that can be utilised in support of media literacy initiatives in the classroom.

Carry out a needs analysis

- This should answer the question of why your initiative is necessary, based on the needs of your audience, e.g. gaps in competences, and/or gaps in provision of services/resources.
- Your initiative is taking place within a wider ecosystem, and it is important to work out how it would benefit the audience/wider sector.

Carry out an assessment of existing evidence to establish whether the project is likely to create measurable impact, and the best way to take your project forward

- Identify and consult any existing evidence, in order to help make your initiative as effective and impactful as possible. Such evidence could be academic research, industry research, or outcomes of other projects in the field.

Identify areas of potential resistance

- Existing beliefs (e.g. scepticism of mainstream media or young people are all 'digital natives') could have a negative impact on your initiative. It is important to try and identify and anticipate potential points of resistance and consider mitigations to limit the risk of negative impact on the initiative.

A good media literacy initiative is inclusive

Inform and engage the wider media literacy community

- No media literacy initiative operates in a vacuum: Identify and engage with other organisations that engage in media literacy activities in your region and/or are trusted intermediaries for your target groups. It is also worth identifying and engaging with any

existing communications and collaboration networks in order to help design your initiative and to build on the experiences of others. Adopting a multi-stakeholder approach can also help to increase the reach and impact of your initiative.

- Think about how your initiative can contribute meaningfully to national expectations, frameworks or curricula for media literacy.
- For example, consider creating an advisory board with representation from several different associated sectors as well as members of your target audience.

✓ A good media literacy initiative is ethical and accessible

Carry out an ethics and accessibility check

- Establish whether there are ethical concerns related to the running of your initiative so as to address these effectively and avoid unintentional harm, particularly when working with children or other vulnerable audiences.
- It is important to consider whether resources/materials have been appropriately designed for readability and accessibility, for example by referring to the [principles of universal design](#).
- Initiatives should be mindful of [human rights](#), including the fundamental right to [freedom of expression](#).

Check for GDPR compliance and any other legal considerations

- A checklist is available [here](#) for GDPR compliance.
- Further attention should be paid to the legislation in the country in which you are working.

Delivery

✓ A good media literacy initiative is transparent

Be transparent about a project's intentions, process and funding

- Clearly explain your goals, motivation and methods on your website, along with any information about your funding sources, to allow participants and the wider community to better understand your initiative.
- Be aware that many people won't recognise the term 'media literacy' and explain your initiative in language that makes sense to your target audience.

✓ A good media literacy initiative is prepared

Carry out a pilot project with a suitable sample size, and integrate lessons learnt

- A pilot project allows you to learn a significant amount about the accessibility, useability and effectiveness of your initiative and make necessary adjustments early.

When possible, benchmark target audience's competences

- Identify a benchmark/baseline to measure against to allow for better target interventions and more effective and informative evaluation. This could involve seeking out existing research and data or testing your target's competences before the initiative.

Ensure that sufficient financial and human resources are in place to complete the project, and to evaluate its impact

- Ensure that a project is sustainable with the necessary resources to achieve its aims: this is essential for success.
- Build in an evaluation plan from the beginning of the project so that you can gather any necessary data for effective evaluation. This could include establishing a control group and/or pre-testing for participants, and ensuring that appropriate resources are set aside for post-test work and analysis.

A good media literacy initiative is adaptable

Carry out an improvement assessment on project design, and be prepared to adapt in case of unexpected developments

- Assess the project at an appropriate point during its implementation to allow you to make changes that can improve its outcomes. Flexibility and mechanisms to adapt are important here.

Continue to engage with the target audience throughout implementation

- Seek feedback from your audience/participants regularly during the course of the intervention to allow you to make tweaks. It can identify barriers and challenges in learning for some, and allow you to provide support where necessary.

Review

Key goals and principles

A good media literacy initiative endures

Seek to extend the project's usefulness to participants

- Give participants material to take away with useful content, links and resources to help ensure that they absorb the material involved.

- Provide participants with a certificate that they could use on their CVs or on social media (adults) or take home (children) to help both increase their confidence and raise awareness of the initiative.

Consider the durability of the initiative's outputs

- Ensure that any resources are easy to use by others, and made available in the public domain, so that your project's usefulness can extend beyond its original term. Check out the [EDMO list of European repositories](#) for places where your resources might be made available to others.
- Even if your project is a one-off or of limited duration, the opportunity might arise to run it again, or some projects provide a framework which can then be adapted by others to include different country- audience- or topic-specific content, while benefiting from the research and design efforts already invested.
- Consider whether any resources developed will remain relevant despite inevitable technological change.
- Keep in mind that people play a key role in transmitting media literacy skills, and where possible, design a project that involves people who can continue to do this, so that an initiative's legacy is more likely to endure. Establishing a network of experts/trainers can help to do this.

Where possible, ensure that resources are available and useable beyond the project's lifetime, and beyond the project's original geographical scope

- Projects that have lasting, reusable resources have potential for wider impact.
- Use resources and cross-border partnerships to promote wider dissemination, including translation and cultural adaptation where appropriate, so that resources could be adapted for other markets.
- Targeted dissemination efforts at specific groups/audiences are likely to be more effective than a generic dissemination strategy.

A good media literacy initiative reflects, shares and evaluates

Evaluate impact as rigorously as possible

- Evaluation of impact is hard but important, and it is helpful to consult the various [toolkits](#), resources and research that have been produced.
- Using more than one different methodology for evaluation of each initiative can make your evaluation more valuable. For evaluation to be informative about whether competences have been acquired as a result of an initiative, use of a control group or pre-/post-testing strategy tends to be preferable (including follow up when possible).
- It is important to acknowledge the limitations of evaluation: you can seek to measure competences including skills and knowledge, but the choices that people make aren't within your control.

Reflect on lessons learnt, including successes, failures and improvements made.

- As well as evaluating impact, reflection is a valuable step in assessing the overall success of a project. It also provides an opportunity to recognise and account for the huge pressure your organisation might be under to deliver results and impact.
- There is also value in seeking and taking into account participants' reflections on the initiative.

Share evaluations and lessons learnt with the wider community.

- Share findings and evaluation in a visible and accessible way to create a wider evidence base of what is and isn't effective that can inform future projects.
- Share what went wrong: this can be hard to do but potentially extremely valuable for those carrying out future work.

Stay up to date about EDMO activities and resources on Digital Media Literacy by subscribing to the EDMO newsletter [here](#).

Endorsements

as of 16 October 2024

“ Guidelines for media literacy play a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness and credibility of media literacy initiatives, particularly in combating misinformation and disinformation. They are essential as they provide a framework for evaluating information's credibility, accuracy, and biases in today's media-saturated environment. ”

All Digital

“ As the guide reiterates, there is no effective one-size-fits-all approach to media literacy. Every community has their own make-up of important topics, media, resources & sensitivities. This guide helps build more initiatives that work best for their target community. ”

Alliance4Europe

Australian
Broadcasting
Corporation

“ Public Service Media organisations are crucial to ensuring that the public are both protected from and educated about the perils that mis- and dis-information can have upon local, national and global democracies. The ABC endorses and congratulates EDMO on the publication of these research-based guidelines which will help steer the production of high-quality media literacy resources and initiatives. ”

Australian Broadcasting Corporation, Australia

“ In the era of digital citizenship, we strongly believe Media Literacy to be a vehicle for the modernization of education. EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives are like road markings for all of us practitioners in education and beyond, who seek to adhere to international guidelines, especially while navigating through misty landscapes. ”

Anna Tsiarta, Cyprus Pedagogical Institute (Ministry of Education), Cyprus

“ The Australian Media Literacy Alliance (AMLA) is pleased to endorse these guidelines as a timely new resource to support best practice approaches to developing, delivering and reviewing effective media literacy initiatives across Europe, and beyond. The guidelines are another important step in enhancing media literacy for all global citizens and communities. ”

Australian Media Literacy Alliance (AMLA), Australia

Baltic Centre for
Media Excellence

“ The hybrid and information warfare tactics we are facing today have made media and information literacy a critical component of our state security systems. As authoritarian regimes pose a growing threat to the democratic world, it is important to strengthen our societies against foreign information manipulation and interference. ”

Baltic Centre for Media Excellence, Latvia

SOUND &
VISION

“ A healthy media ecosystem thrives on self-aware and informed media users. As part of the BENEDMO hub, Sound & Vision fully endorses this approach, emphasising each individual's active role in shaping that ecosystem. The EDMO Media Literacy Guidelines help in this regard, adopting an empowering approach by equipping individuals with the necessary tools to effectively navigate disinformation, rather than solely focusing on the challenges. With many organisations committed to enhancing media literacy, these guidelines will empower professionals and institutions to develop, distribute, and evaluate impactful interventions, ultimately making a positive difference. ”

Beeld en Geluid (The Netherlands Institute of Sound and Vision), The Netherlands

Bibliothèques
Sans Frontières
BELGIQUE

“ More than ever, the challenges posed by disinformation and misinformation call for exacting, sustainable media literacy programmes, resonating with their target group(s) as well as the wider media literacy community and digital media ecosystem. Bibliothèques Sans Frontières celebrates EDMO's initiative to bind all media literacy contributors by common goals and principles, and will follow and promote such guidelines through the development of its resources, deployment of its activities and collaborations with other organizations and experts in the media literacy field. ”

Bibliothèques Sans Frontières, Belgique

CIVIC
RESILIENCE
INITIATIVE

“ We agree with the EDMO guidelines as they closely align with our existing practices in media literacy initiatives. We already follow most of these principles, such as setting clear goals, using evidence-based approaches, and promoting inclusivity. This alignment helps ensure that our projects are ethical, and adaptable, and empower participants to critically engage with the media. ”

Civic Resilience Initiative, Lithuania

COUNCIL FOR
MEDIA SERVICES

“ Council for Media Services fully supports EDMO guidelines aimed at increasing media literacy in the EU environment. These principle-based guidelines seek to streamline projects and enable better utilization of resources in this area. As such, the effectiveness of media literacy initiatives could be significantly increased by a common approach supported by the guidelines. ”

Council for Media Services, Slovakia

verificat ““ These guidelines are designed to enhance media literacy by providing a solid framework inspired by research and expert methodologies. They align with fact-checking practices and promote critical thinking skills through a better understanding of the media landscape and how our emotions interact with it. By using meaningful, real-life examples adapted to various audiences, the guidelines support more effective learning experiences and help build resilience against mis- and disinformation. ””

[Cristina Figueras, Verificat, Spain](#)

DW Akademie ““ As a media development organization dedicated to fostering trust in public interest media, we endorse EDMO’s principles as a unifying framework for media literacy initiatives. By emphasizing empowerment over protection, these principles promote active engagement and critical thinking, helping individuals navigate the media landscape. Their focus on inclusivity ensures diverse voices are heard, while collaboration with existing organizations enhances reach and impact—central to DWA's MIL approach. By aligning with this framework, we can create cohesive media literacy programs that educate and build a more informed public, ultimately strengthening media integrity. ””

[Deutsche Welle Akademie, Germany](#)

DCN Global ““ The concept of Media Literacy, whether in its practice or in the development of public policies, must reserve its integrity. In times of disinformation, media literacy is one of the important actions to maintain the integrity of information, and the full development of citizenship. Therefore, the care in preserving working principles is fundamental. The work of the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO) has been fundamental in this field for years. And the recent EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives is a pivotal tool for any organization wishing to develop these practices. DCN Global hopes that the quality of the European Digital Media Observatory will serve as inspiration for other materials in the field of Media Literacy that are still scarce, especially beyond the European continent. ””

[DCN Global](#)

MENO AVILYS ““ In many European countries, media literacy is developed through ongoing projects, short-term initiatives, training, and professional development offered by various institutions, NGOs, educational and cultural organizations, and individuals. Therefore, it is crucial to have guidelines that remind diverse stakeholders of the key components of effective media literacy initiatives. ””

[Dovilė Alėbaitė, Meno Avylis, Lithuania](#)

“ These guidelines are an important step towards ensuring there are high standards of media literacy across Europe and that any organisation wishing to implement media literacy can do so effectively. ”

Eileen Culloty, DCU Institute for Media, Democracy and Society, Ireland

“ EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives is a necessary milestone for the European media literacy community while also supporting the development of Digital information literacy to keep us future-proofing media education on new technological challenges on what is accurate and genuine online. Great work EDMO! ”

FaktaBaari, Finland

“ Since its foundation (2009), GILM’s work has been dedicated to bringing and maintaining Media Literacy (ML) in the national public agenda, to contribute to a better articulation among different agents/projects and to the improvement of the practice of media literacy education through the promotion of its own ML initiatives. GILM recognises these guidelines will offer an exceptional blueprint to help the diversity of promoters and can certainly be applied across diverse ML initiatives, making them versatile tools for addressing a broad range of challenges of the complex media ecosystem. ”

Fernanda Bonacho, GILM, Portugal

“ FORMA.Azione throughout the last 8 years have been increasingly working in European projects at both transnational and national level, focused on combating online hate speech and disinformation, by equipping people with an appropriate set of knowledge and skills to safely, wisely and consciously navigate the online environment, including social media.

We think that the Guidelines are a very relevant tool to help both professionals in the media and media literacy sector and the large audience to further reflect on the importance of referring to and adopt recommendations and working methods detailed in the guidelines, so as to fully benefit from the online media resources. ”

FORMA.Azione, Italy

“ The Gibraltar Regulatory Authority fully endorses the EDMO Guidelines as this will play a vital role in fostering critical thinking skills and helping people navigate today’s complex media landscape. These guidelines will help create media literacy initiatives to counter misinformation and help promote informed and responsible engagement across digital and traditional media platforms ”

Francis Trenado, Gibraltar Regulatory Authority, Gibraltar, United Kingdom

“ Thank you for noting the importance of journalism; a critical early lesson. Journalism differs radically from other online content, serving as a weapon against the daily onslaught of the fake, the imaginary and the truly dangerous, and also as an approach by students and teachers to digital media literacy itself. ”

Global Youth & News Media

“ The EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives are essential for ensuring that projects developed in this field are meaningful, replicable, subject to reflection and evaluation from their inception. CEU - Cooperativa de Ensino Universitário, C.R.L., located in Lisbon at Rua de Santa Marta, 56, founding institution of the Universidade Autónoma de Lisboa, endorses and implements these guidelines in its media literacy initiatives and R&D projects. ”

Grupo Autónoma, Portugal

“ European Schoolnet warmly welcomes the EDMO guidelines for effective media literacy initiatives. Over the last decade, we have seen increased support at European and national level for media literacy initiatives and critical thinking, often with a view to promote active and responsible digital citizenship. This set of principles and guidelines will help policy makers and educators to structure their thinking on how to make media literacy work in practice, adopting an evidence-based, inclusive and empowering approach, with clearly defined learning goals and longer-term societal impact in mind. ”

Hans Martens, European Schoolnet

“ These thorough, complex, and sophisticated guidelines are an excellent tool for implementing our future media literacy programmes. It offers a precious common framework for reflection for the European media literacy community. ”

Idea Foundation, Hungary

“ Desperately needed and exceptionally refined, multidimensional, inclusive, adaptable to different contexts and capacities, retroactively applicable to the evaluation of already concluded initiatives, but also future-proof - the EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives are a valuable (and values-based!) contribution to the entire community of MIL and digital literacy practitioners, researchers, scholars, policy-makers and project developers. ”

Iglika Ivanova, Media Literacy Coalition, Bulgaria

“ In order to navigate the complex media landscape we find ourselves in, media literacy is an essential skill. These guidelines give a clear roadmap for the development of effective media literacy initiatives. ”

[Jane McGarrigle, Webwise, Ireland](#)

“ Media literacy is essential for a thriving democracy, and these cohesive guidelines ensure the highest standards of inclusivity, transparency and ethical practices. SOUK is delighted to endorse these guidelines, which foster a healthy sector that evolves with the changing media landscape and works toward shared goals. ”

[Jillian Rolnick, Shout Out, United Kingdom](#)

“ Lie Detectors advocates for media literacy to be recognised as a core literacy alongside reading, writing and counting. The EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives are a crucial stepping stone for this to be realisable. They are clear, actionable and will help equip the public with the tools to resist disinformation and polarisation, and understand how to find reliable facts. ”

[Juliane von Reppert-Bismarck, Lie Detectors](#)

“ In the era of digital convergence, Creative Greece embraces EDMO’s Guidelines for effective media literacy initiatives, as they not only establish a global framework for developing actions and measuring impact but also underscore the significance of the “power of joining forces” by the key EU players in the digital and creative industries. ”

[Leonidas Christopoulos, Creative Greece, Greece](#)

“ In Maldita we know by experience that fostering media literacy and critical thinking education is indispensable in the battle against disinformation. The EDMO’s guidelines are an excellent tool for every organisation that needs to develop a media literacy initiative from scratch, considering the importance of an evidence-based approach, transparency and community, among others. ”

[Maldita.es, Spain](#)

“ Many media education proposals today are misaligned with current demands and lack emphasis on diversity and transparency. EDMO’s proposal helps navigate these challenges, aligning with present realities and promoting diversity in actions to meet today’s media education needs. ”

[Maria José Brites, CICANT - Lusófona, Portugal](#)

“ MediaSmarts/HabiloMédias is glad to endorse the EDMO guidelines for effective media literacy initiatives. These will be a valuable tool for organizations and governments worldwide and are an important step towards placing media literacy on a more solid foundation of research and evidence. ”

Matthew Johnson, MediaSmarts/HabiloMédias, Canada

“ MLI wholeheartedly supports the EDMO goal of elevating media literacy across Europe and beyond by offering clear, practical principles that support new and existing initiatives. ”

We applaud the fact that these 12 key principles cover all stages of an initiative – development, implementation, and review – focusing on clear goals, inclusivity, ethical practices, adaptability, and more. By following these guidelines, we believe that media literacy projects will be more effective and have greater, measurable impact. We will use these guidelines when developing our own initiatives, and we will also encourage our cross-sector membership to do the same. ”

Media Literacy Ireland

“ I’m delighted to see EDMO taking on the important and challenging task of developing and editing standards and best practices for media literacy. As we face a rapidly changing media environment with the growth of AI and complex social and political dynamics, it is increasingly important to ground efforts in a resilient set of processes for maintaining quality, and ensuring ethical and equitable outcomes. ”

Mimi Ito, Connected Learning Lab, University of California, Irvine, United States

“ One of the core reasons behind the establishment of the Macedonian Media Literacy Network (MLN) is cooperation between different stakeholders when conducting ML projects and activities to ensure their greater efficiency and results. We find the EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives to be a welcomed tool when planning and executing each phase of a project cycle. ”

MLN - Media Literacy Network, Republic of North Macedonia

“ The perspective of fighting disinformation encourages us to think of educational activities as based on a long-term and carefully planned process considering all the effects, appropriate selection of the target group and selection of the best tools to reach them. Creating guidelines for effective media literacy initiatives is one such step towards better awareness of the process and improving its quality. ”

NASK, Poland

“ Many people and organizations want to promote media literacy, but may not know where to start. The European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO) Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives provide straightforward principles and steps for developing and enacting effective, inclusive, and reflective media literacy projects. The EDMO guidelines are flexible enough to support a range of approaches and strategies for media literacy that are needed now more than ever in our changing media landscape. ”

NAMLE - National Association for Media Literacy Education, United States

“ Clear, knowledgeable, actionable. These guidelines are a valuable tool for designing effective and impactful media literacy interventions. ”

Nicola Bruno, Dataninja, Italy

“ These guidelines present valuable and practical insights that are well-aligned with and will greatly complement our ongoing and future initiatives in the field of media literacy. ”

Nino Grdzlishvili, Communications Commission, Georgia

“ The Guidelines have the potential to improve the work of small MIL teams and organisations, like ourselves. They provide a clear path to how we approach new MIL interventions in a consistent and structured manner. This is a tool of condensed expertise now available to everyone in the MIL ecosystem – expertise which is, very commonly, unaffordable to small actors in the field. ”

NTCenter, Bulgaria

“ The desired impact of media literacy projects developed in Europe can only be guaranteed through ongoing reflection and evaluation, from the project's design to the definition of its sustainability. Therefore, we endorse the EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives ”

Obercom-Observatório da Comunicação, Portugal

“ These guidelines provide a useful, practical contribution to encouraging good practice for media literacy interventions, complementing our own work in this area. ”

Ofcom, United Kingdom

“ In the context of the growing popularity of media literacy projects, the proposed guidelines serve as a wise roadmap for all entities that are currently planning or will plan new initiatives in the future. They enable us to ask the right questions at an early stage of work,

ensuring that the project addresses the actual needs of the target group and brings about real social change. ””

Patryk Zakrzewski, Demagog Association, Poland

”” We, as the Education Group, have been working for decades at the intersection of education, technology, and media. While our primary focus is in Austria, we are also involved in various international initiatives and projects in these areas. Especially in these challenging, fast-paced times of opinion-making and fake news, it is more important than ever for us to implement high-quality, well-thought-out measures in the field of media education that consider the needs of the target audience, demonstrate impact, and make their results widely accessible. The “EDMO guidelines for effective media literacy initiatives” provide an excellent foundation for this! ””

Peter Eiselmair, EDUgroup, Austria

”” As we’ve been running our own media literacy programmes for many years, we welcome any comprehensive and easy-to-grasp guidelines. The EDMO guidelines comprise the most important features of effective media literacy training. ””

Peter Jančárik, Seznam.cz, Czech Republic

”” PL2030 is looking forward to spreading the news on the EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives in Europe. Public libraries have a high potential to provide inclusive innovative MIL activities. The guidelines will support and help public libraries to contribute to enhancing public resilience against online mis- and disinformation. ””

Public Libraries 2030

”” The EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives will help a new generation of practitioners from many different fields gain insight on best practices for designing, implementing, and assessing media literacy programs. Using these guidelines will help people develop programs that have a wide impact and substantial reach. The guidelines will inspire significant innovation in the development of new programs and services. Most importantly, these guidelines reflect and embody the core empowering values of media literacy education as articulated by the global knowledge community. ””

Renee Hobbs, Media Education Lab, United States

”” These new guidelines offer a mechanism whereby government agencies, platforms, funders and anyone interested in promoting good quality and effective media literacy initiatives can benchmark their own work and the work of others. Our goal is to grow a body of

useful resources and good practices to back-up these guidelines including their translation and localisation to make them as widely applicable as possible. ””

Sally Reynolds, Media & Learning Association

”” The EDMO Media Literacy Guidelines are a key resource for improving media literacy efforts across Europe. They provide a structured, evidence-based approach that enables organisations, educators and other practitioners to develop effective media literacy initiatives, thereby building public resilience to misinformation and disinformation. The guidelines are organised around 12 key principles divided into three sections: development, implementation and review. These comprehensive principles address both practical and ethical considerations, ensuring that media literacy initiatives are inclusive, adaptable and sustainable. Whether for new or experienced practitioners, the guidelines provide valuable support for improving the design and implementation of media literacy campaigns aimed at combating misinformation and disinformation. ””

SCRIPT - Service de Coordination de la Recherche et de l'Innovation pédagogiques et technologiques, Luxembourg

”” As demand for media literacy has never been higher, these guidelines are an invaluable resource to help organisations develop and evaluate their initiatives. ””

Shane Murphy, DCU University, Ireland

”” The EFCSN is the voice of European fact-checkers who uphold and promote the highest standards of fact-checking and media literacy in their effort to combat misinformation for the public benefit. We welcome the EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives. They are comprehensive, actionable and aim to enhance the public's resilience against mis- and disinformation - a goal which the EFCSN shares. ””

Stephan Mundges, EFCSN

”” In today's borderless media landscape, having shared guidelines for media literacy is very useful. At Tenk, we support these guidelines as they encourage critical thinking and promote quality education in media literacy, empowering individuals to engage with information responsibly ””

Tenk, Norway

”” Transitions is proud to endorse the EDMO Guidelines for Effective Media Literacy Initiatives, which provide a vital framework for strengthening public resilience against disinformation. As a nonprofit organization dedicated to media and digital education for seniors,

we deeply value the focus on inclusivity, critical thinking, and ethical practices. These principles align with our mission to create an accessible and supportive learning environment for all generations, and we are fully committed to advancing these efforts.

Transitions, Czech Republic

“ Planning and executing media literacy initiatives that are both thought provoking and engaging, as well as effective and impactful, is a challenging task. EDMO guidelines for the effective media literacy initiatives offer a much-needed guidance and inspiration for different stakeholders – from civil society, educators, policy makers – working on the topic of media literacy.

University of Tartu, Institute of Social Studies, Estonia

“ Media literacy today is the ability to communicate more creatively than ChatGPT and understand why that matters.

Žarko Čižmar, Telecentar, Croatia

Additional Endorsements

as of 16 October 2024

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